

ON THE QUANTITATIVE ESTIMATION OF BERYLLIUM. PART I. AS BARIUM FLUOBERYLLATE GRAVIMETRICALLY

BY R. K. DUTTA AND A. K. SEN GUPTA

A gravimetric method for the estimation of beryllium has been described. Beryllium with fluoride ion affords a BeF_4^{2-} ion, and when a barium salt is added to this solution, it effects a quantitative precipitation of BaBeF_4 . The p_n of the solution was maintained at approx. 4. The formation of barium fluoride and the corroding action of hydrofluoric acid on glass are prevented by addition of boric acid.

There are several gravimetric, volumetric and colorimetric methods for the estimation of beryllium. In the gravimetric methods beryllium is either weighed as BeO or $\text{Be}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$. In the methods where beryllium is weighed as BeO by ignition, it is precipitated as $\text{Be}(\text{OH})_2$ by ammonia gas or by ammonium nitrite and methyl alcohol (Moser and Singer, *Monatsh.*, 1927, 48, 675) or by other hydrolytic reagents (Akizayama, *Japan Analyst*, 1953, 2, 116; Quadrat and Svejda, *Chem. Obzor.*, 1950, 25, 85) or as tannin complex (Moser and Niessner, *Monatsh.*, 1927, 48, 113). Beryllium is also weighed as $\text{Be}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ by ignition, after precipitating as BeNH_4PO_4 (Moser and Singer, *ibid.*, 1927, 48, 679).

From the analogy between SO_4^{2-} ion and BeF_4^{2-} ion (Sarkar and Ray, this *Journal*, 1929, 6, 987), it was presumed that a method might be developed for the estimation of beryllium on account of sparing solubility of BaBeF_4 like BaSO_4 . In the present communication, a new method for the gravimetric estimation of beryllium has been described, in which beryllium is weighed as BaBeF_4 .

Principle of the Method.—Beryllium ion with fluoride ion forms a very stable BeF_4^{2-} ion, according to the equation

The fluoberyllate ion is then precipitated as BaBeF_4 by adding barium salt.

It is known that barium affords sparingly soluble BaF_2 from alkali fluoride solutions. But in the presence of boric acid no precipitate of BaF_2 was found to occur below $p_n \approx 5$. So, it is necessary to make the precipitation of BaBeF_4 at p_n lower than 5. Again, if p_n of fluoride solution is lowered, the action of hydrofluoric acid on glass containers also increases, leading to the formation of silico-fluoride ion which provides sparingly soluble precipitate with barium ion.

In the present method the solution was maintained at $p_n \approx 4$. The action of hydrofluoric acid on glass container was prevented by the addition of boric acid, which also inhibited the formation of BaF_2 at this p_n . It was found, however, that BaBeF_4 could be precipitated quantitatively at a p_n as low as 2.5 when the concentration of fluoride in solution was low.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Beryllium nitrate solution was prepared by dissolving Schering and Kahlbaum's beryllium nitrate and standardised in the usual way by precipitating beryllium as $\text{Be}(\text{OH})_2$ by ammonia gas and estimating as BeO .

Sodium fluoride (2.5% ; Pure, E. Merk) was heated at 900° - 1000° for several hours to break silico-fluoride. It was then powdered and a solution was made. It was filtered through a fine filter paper and was stored in polyethylene bottle. All the other reagents used were of G.R. quality.

Procedure.—Beryllium nitrate solution (10 c. c.) containing 22 mg. to 7 mg. of beryllium was taken in a 400 c. c. beaker ; 5 drops of Wesselow's indicator and then 50 c. c. of 2.5% sodium fluoride solution were added. The volume of the solution was made to 300 c. c. and to it 4 g. of boric acid was added and stirred to dissolve it. Hydrochloric acid solution was then added to the above solution until its green colour had changed to violet. The solution was heated to boiling and 15 c.c. of hot barium chloride solution added dropwise with stirring. The solution was then kept on a hot water-bath for one hour, covering the beaker with a clock-glass which helped in maintaining the volume of the solution almost constant. The solution was stirred several times during this period. The precipitate settled down in one hour and the solution was filtered through a sintered glass crucible by suction. The precipitate was taken into the crucible by hot water and was washed till the issuing filtrate was free of chloride. Generally, washing for 8 to 10 times with 4 c. c. of water at a time was sufficient. Then it was washed twice with alcohol. The BaBeF_4 was dried at 110° - 120° for one hour and cooled and weighed to a constant weight. It was found that one hour's drying gave constant weight.

TABLE I

Be taken	2.5% NaF soln.	Boric acid.	BaBeF_4 found.	Be calc.	% Error.
21.58 mg.	50 c.c.	0.5 g.	0.5320 g.	21.52 mg.	-0.28
"	"	"	0.5353	21.66	+0.37
"	"	1.0	0.5311	21.49	-0.42
"	"	"	0.5301	21.45	-0.60
15.15	40	0.35	0.3744	15.07	-0.53
"	"	"	0.3747	15.16	+0.07
"	"	2.0	0.3748	15.17	+0.13
"	"	"	0.3737	15.12	-0.20
"	"	4.0	0.3743	15.15	± 0
"	"	"	0.3744	15.15	± 0
"	"	6.0	0.3729	15.09	-0.40
"	60	0.37	0.3769	15.25	+0.66
"	100	5.0	0.3722	15.06	-0.60
"	"	"	0.3758	15.20	+0.33
"	"	"	"	"	"
7.575	"	"	0.1881	7.610	+0.46
"	"	"	0.1862	7.534	-0.54

* From the weight of BaBeF_4 found.

The anions (such as sulphate, silicofluoride, etc.), which produce insoluble precipitates with barium, and the cations, which afford insoluble fluorides at a p_H lower than 5, should not be present in the solution. Potassium fluoride must not be used as the source of fluoride because it forms with boric acid KBF_4 which being sparingly soluble and isomorphous with $BaBeF_4$ precipitates with it. The amount of fluoride added should be about 1 to 2 g. in the total volume of solution. Because it was seen that at higher concentrations of fluoride than 2.5 g. in the total volume of solution, error was more than 1%. The results are shown in Table I.

Further work on the estimation of beryllium in beryl is under investigation and will be shortly published.

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INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
DEPARTMENT OF PURE CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA-9.

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